

THE WAYS OF IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION SKILLS

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Annotation: This article give information about rapid developments in invented technologies lead educational institutions to effectively integrate these technologies into the teaching-learning processes. However, both institutions and individuals face different obstacles because of these integration processes.

Key words: Pre-service teacher education, computer competencies, technology vision

Educational systems are based on teacher and curriculum concepts. Effectiveness and efficiency of an educational system rely on these two inter-related concepts and the harmony between them. Any problems appearing in either of these concepts will decrease the quality of the educational system, as a result affecting the learners. For this reason, the quality of an educational system should be parallel to the quality of teachers trained. Moreover, the quality of a teacher will be in harmony with the curriculum focused knowledge, skills and the attitudes acquired by the preservice teachers. Technological and computer competencies of teachers are important dimensions of this quality. Due to large investments of technology in many educational institutions, teachers are required to integrate technology into curriculum and classroom activities. For this reason, teacher education programs are reshaped and enhanced with the courses trying to infuse the use of various technologies. This enhancement includes the knowledge and skills necessary to use and integrate technology effectively. Besides, teachers' attitudes and beliefs toward technology usage should result in a positive one. Therefore, teachers should be designated in such a way that besides knowing how to use technologies effectively, they have to be empowered to use technologies to develop learners understanding

and to support constructivism, cooperative learning and problem-based learning. Technology Integration into Teacher Education Programs Almost all education institutions across the world are rethinking and reorganizing the manner in which they are preparing pre-service and in-service teachers to use technology in order to enhance classroom instruction. Then again, higher education institutions are also seeking new strategies to support the process of technology integration, as they are the leaders and models of technology diffusion. Teacher education programs are intended not only to give occupational and branch of learning expertise but also the vision for integrating technology into the teaching-learning process. Consequently, "...schools, colleges, and departments of education have sought not only to provide courses on educational technology but also to infuse technology into the teacher education curriculum such that preservice teachers experience technology-rich instruction both as students". Higher education institutions are making great efforts to overcome the obstacles posed by information and communication technologies (ICT) and how to disseminate technology into classrooms. Many research studies have been carried out to find the correct pathways for effective integration, each pointing out different variables affecting the integration process. Among these variables, the lack of role-modeling by professors, due to poor technology competencies of professors, is the one which plays an important role in the effectiveness of the teacher education process. Effective integration requires the existence of the necessary hardware and software, effective usage of resources, adequate in-service training opportunities, well-prepared professors and innovative implementation strategies for faculties. Accordingly, the professors' technology-competency levels, perceptions on the use of technology and obstacles they face are the factors which should be investigated carefully in order to propose appropriate strategies for effective technology integration.

The article findings describe what pre-service teachers require to integrate technology, especially computers, into classroom activities. Only a small portion of

the participants had negative attitudes towards computers and a lack of computer skills at the beginning of the semester. This negative attitude might stem from two reasons, a fear because of a lack of computer skills, and no prior knowledge about how to use technology in their subject fields. However, at the end of the course all of the participants had obtained positive attitudes and enhanced their computer skills. Since all of the pre-service teachers were willing to participate in the course and enhance their knowledge base, the gap among these pre-service teachers disappeared, and most of them successfully completed the entire assignments. Furthermore, pre-service teachers understood how to use technology in their pre, during and post class activities, since they had the opportunities to practice what they had learnt. As the instructor observed, the mathematics group had more difficulties in altering content in a visual form than the biology-chemistry group preparing materials. This result might be caused by subject field, since mathematics is not as concrete as the other subjects. Moreover, the mathematics group were required to be more creative in order to fulfill the course goals, since the resources and examples of materials in mathematics were more limited in comparison to other subject fields. Although, the findings of the study showed satisfaction for both pre-service teachers and the instructor, preservice teachers declared their need for an advanced contribution for integrating technology into their future classrooms. This result revealed that just one goal for achieving the goal of effective teaching via using technology is not enough which is also mentioned in the literature by many. Hence, teachers have to build a knowledge base on how to routinely integrate technology into their and given more opportunities to apply instructional technology prior to their real-life experiences. This study profoundly showed that the courses and the course content offered to pre-service teachers should constantly be revised to address current technology and its use in educational environment. These courses should be shaped in order to progress from computer competencies to instructional planning and technology integration. Accordingly, "the most important competencies for

teachers appear to be the knowledge and skills to make computers a seamless part of the school curriculum". In the process of a course-long intervention, prospective teachers not only increased their skills with computers and technology integration but also demonstrated incorporating changes in technology into their teaching and future plans. In other words, pre-service teachers experienced the power of technology to enhance traditional classroom instruction. Furthermore, this study underlined the need for pre-service teachers to effectively use and integrate technology into instructional processes. Although the present study concluded with hopeful results, the real question that we have to answer is, "what kind of curriculum will allow pre-service teachers to gain sufficient technology vision?" It is obvious that increasing the number of courses aimed at teachers with the necessary skills and to provide instructional approaches to effectively integrate technology, will probably make a difference. If this increase includes model teachers of the same field, together with various skills to use technology to create constructivist and cooperative learning environments, this would be preferable. On the other hand, what if the change in the curriculum should not happen immediately? Then we have to answer the question, "how to use only one 'concrete' course to allow pre-service teachers gain enough technology vision?" Any technology integration process has many barriers to overcome. Trying to overcome these barriers in a very limited time should certainly end with changes in the learners' knowledge, skills, attitudes and vision. But the satisfactoriness of these changes will be an ongoing and never-ending discussion until no technological innovations are proposed. Hence, although one can find numerous similar articles in the literature that produced similar results, in Turkish context, this article has valuable information for those teaching in non-theses teaching programs.

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